

CORELATIVE EVALUATION OF POST TRAUMATIC HEMOTHORAX ON PLAIN RADIOGRAPHY AND COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15835294>

Keywords

Post-traumatic hemothorax,
 Thoracic trauma, Plain
 radiography, Chest X-ray,
 Computed tomography, CT
 imaging, Radiographic correlation,
 Imaging accuracy, Diagnostic
 sensitivity, Pleural fluid,
 Hemothorax detection.

Article History

Received on 02 June 2025
 Accepted on 02 July 2025
 Published on 08 July 2025

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Post-traumatic hemothorax is the accumulation of blood in the pleural cavity following chest trauma and requires prompt diagnosis to prevent serious complications. Plain radiography is widely used as an initial imaging tool but may miss small or posterior collections. In contrast, Computed Tomography (CT) provides detailed visualization, making it more accurate in detecting hemothorax and associated injuries. However, the correlation between radiographic and CT findings in post-traumatic hemothorax remains insufficiently explored, highlighting the need for comparative evaluation to improve diagnostic accuracy and patient outcomes.

OBJECTIVE: To evaluate the correlation between plain radiography and computed tomography in the assessment of post-traumatic hemothorax.

METHODOLOGY: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Radiology Department of Children Hospital, Lahore, over a period of four months. A total of 40 patients with suspected thoracic trauma were selected through convenient sampling. All patients underwent both plain chest radiography and high-resolution 640-slice CT scanning of the thorax. Imaging included standard PA chest X-rays and thin-slice CT with multiplanar reconstructions. Patients with pre-existing lung disease or incomplete imaging were excluded. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.

RESULTS: This study included 40 patients with suspected thoracic trauma, with a male predominance (67.5%). Most participants were young to middle-aged adults, primarily in the 23–30 age group. Chest pain was reported in 47.5% of cases, rib fractures in 37.5%, and dyspnea in 27.5%. CT findings showed hyperdense pleural fluid in 40%, lung collapse in 35%, and atelectasis in 32.5%. On plain radiography, increased density was noted in 45%, blurring of diaphragm and heart borders in 35%, and costophrenic angle abnormalities in 25%. Chi-square analysis revealed no significant associations between key clinical and radiological variables, though a potential trend was observed between hyperdense

pleural fluid and costophrenic angle changes. These findings highlight the diagnostic value of CT in detecting post-traumatic hemothorax, often revealing abnormalities that are not clearly evident on chest radiographs.

CONCLUSION: The study concluded that computed tomography (CT) is a valuable diagnostic tool in evaluating thoracic trauma, revealing critical findings such as hyperdense pleural fluid, lung collapse, and atelectasis that may be missed on plain radiography. While chest X-rays showed limited sensitivity, CT provided more detailed assessment, particularly in identifying post-traumatic hemothorax. These results support the use of CT for accurate diagnosis and improved management of thoracic injuries

INTRODUCTION

A hemothorax, or blood in pleural cavity, results from intrathoracic hemorrhage from lacerated lung parenchyma, the heart, great vessels or their branches, the diaphragm, or intercostal or chest wall vessels. Hemothorax as a specific clinicopathological entity can be defined in two ways. Morphologically, Hemothorax is a pathologic accumulation of blood within the pleural cavity, between the lung surface and inner chest wall. From the clinical viewpoint, Hemothorax is defined as the extraction of pleural fluid with a hematocrit ranging from at least 25–50% of peripheral blood. It is important to realize that even Hemothorax can appear as a hemorrhagic effusion with lower levels of hematocrit because there is a significant dilution in 3–4 days.¹ The majority of haemothorax instances are associated with open or closed chest injuries or operations like central lines, thoracentesis, pleural biopsy, or catheterisation.² Catamenial haemothorax accounts for 14% of thoracic endometriosis syndrome cases, whereas 73% of cases have catamenial pneumothorax, 7% have catamenial haemoptysis, and 6% have pulmonary nodules.³ One of the vascular causes of hemothorax is rupture of the descending aorta, which, because of the close proximity of the pleural cavity, first affects the left pleural and mediastinal area. Blood vessel tearing that happens spontaneously is more common in people with blood vessel weakening disorders (like some types of Ehlers-Danlos syndrome), blood vessel malformation disorders (like Rendu-Osler-Weber syndrome), or bleeding

disorders (like hemophilia and Glanzmann thrombasthenia).⁴ A damage to the lung, such as a rib fracture, a gunshot or knife wound to the chest, or some medical operations, can result in collapsed lung.⁵ About 5–30% of individuals with significant respiratory problems get Hemothorax. Depending on the kind and extent of trauma, such as blunt or penetrating chest injuries, the occurrence of post-traumatic Hemothorax and pneumothorax varies about 5–30% of people who have had substantial chest injuries experience hemothorax.⁶ Hemothorax can be caused by three main factors: trauma, iatrogenic, or spontaneous. The most frequent causes 13–15 of the roughly 16,000–30,000 annual deaths is traumatic thoracic trauma.^{16, 17} Iatrogenic and, less frequently, spontaneous come next. The incidence of blunt trauma (73.3%), iatrogenic trauma (25.0%), and spontaneous trauma (1.7%), among older patients, has been recorded. Major arteries including the aorta, internal mammary arteries, and intercostal arteries may be implicated by any one of the three Hemothorax origins, which could result in tension Hemothorax, exsanguination and even death.⁷ The symptoms are dependent on how well the lung functions, which are compromised by the blood clot on that side, are doing. The degree of bleeding determines the rate at which the lungs collapse and the ensuing rise in tachypnea, dyspnea, and cyanosis.⁸ Hemothorax is characterized by diminished or absent breath sound, dullness to percussion, tachypnea, and tachycardia as clinical symptoms.⁹

Anxiety, quick breathing, restlessness, shock, and pale, chilly, clammy skin are some of the warning signs.¹⁰ The most popular method for diagnosing a Hemothorax is a chest X-ray. Although it is desirable to take X-rays with the patient upright (an erect chest X-ray), if this is not possible, the patient may be placed on their back (supine). Acute pleural bleeding on CT causes a fluid-fluid level, high attenuation material within the pleural effusion, or enhanced attenuation of pleural fluid. Upon defibrillation, the fluid in the pleural space cannot be differentiated from any other type of effusion on CT scans. By measuring the attenuation value, CT can be used to identify the type of pleural fluid in trauma situations. The attenuation of blood in the pleural space is usually between 35 and 70 HU. When interpreting chest trauma CT, it should be standard practice to evaluate pleural fluid attenuation in order to differentiate acute blood from simple fluid.¹¹ Chest tube insertion, also known as tube thoracostomy, is the most significant and often used treatment for Hemothorax. It is essential for emptying the stored blood and enabling the lung to expand once more. To avoid respiratory discomfort and complications including lung collapse, this technique is crucial in cases with moderate to massive Hemothorax. In addition, blood transfusions and fluid resuscitation are essential to maintain blood pressure and avoid shock, particularly cases of considerable blood loss.¹² Globally prevalence of Late Hemothorax, a rare complication, exhibits a prevalence up to 12.1%.¹³

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Radiology Department of Children Hospital, Lahore, over a period of four months. A total of 40 patients with suspected thoracic trauma were included in the study using non-probability convenient sampling. The purpose was to evaluate and correlate the presence of post-traumatic hemothorax using

plain chest radiography and computed tomography (CT). All patients underwent both imaging modalities—standard posterior-anterior chest X-rays and high-resolution 640-slice CT scans of the thorax. CT imaging included thin-slice axial views with multiplanar reconstructions. Patients with pre-existing pulmonary diseases or incomplete imaging records were excluded. Data were collected on key radiographic indicators such as costophrenic angle blunting and increased opacity, and CT indicators such as hyperdense pleural fluid and lung collapse. The data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Chi-square tests were applied to explore the association between clinical findings and radiological features, with a significance threshold set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

A total of 40 individuals were included in the study, with males accounting for 67.5% ($n=27$) and females for 32.5% ($n=13$), indicating a male-dominant sample. Age distribution was skewed toward younger adults, with the highest representation in the 23–30-year group (32.5%), followed by 31–38 years (25%). The distribution progressively declined across older age groups, with the lowest representation observed in the 55–62 age group (2.5%). This suggests that the majority of cases examined in the study were among young to middle-aged adults. Clinically, traumatic injury was observed in exactly half of the participants (50%), suggesting a balanced distribution of trauma presence. Chest pain was reported by 47.5% of participants, and rib fractures were identified in 37.5%. Dyspnea was reported in 27.5% of the sample, while clammy skin was the least frequently reported symptom, present in only 20%. These data suggest that while general symptoms like chest pain and rib fractures are relatively common in the sample, more severe or systemic indicators such as dyspnea and clammy skin were less prevalent. CT and X-ray evaluations provided additional

diagnostic insights. Atelectasis was identified in 32.5% of individuals, hyperdense pleural fluid in 40%, and collapsed lung in 35%. These findings suggest a relatively high burden of structural and physiological changes in the lungs. On chest X-ray, increased density was present in 45% of the sample, blurring of the diaphragm and heart borders in 35%, and costophrenic angle abnormalities in 25%. These imaging abnormalities correlate partially with the clinical symptoms but also suggest the presence of subclinical or radiologically significant pathology not always reflected in reported symptoms. Chi-square tests were conducted to explore potential associations between key clinical and radiological variables. Cross-tabulation between gender and both chest pain and rib fracture revealed no statistically significant associations (p-values ranging from 0.138 to 0.370), suggesting that the occurrence of these conditions is independent of gender. Similarly, no significant associations were found between collapsed lung and blurring of diaphragm and heart borders (all p-values > 0.5), nor between increased density and atelectasis (all

p-values > 0.05). The relationship between hyperdense pleural fluid and costophrenic angle changes approached statistical significance (p-values between 0.016 and 0.062), but remained above the standard threshold, indicating only a potential trend without confirmatory evidence of association. The data highlight that while traumatic injuries and associated clinical symptoms such as chest pain and rib fractures are frequently encountered, more severe signs like dyspnea, clammy skin, and lung collapse are relatively less common. Radiological findings such as increased density and hyperdense pleural fluid are common, although they do not always correlate with specific clinical features. Statistical analyses indicate that most clinical and imaging findings operate independently within the sample, with no significant gender-based differences or predictive relationships between paired variables. These findings suggest the need for further research with larger sample sizes to explore potential interactions and improve the clinical utility of radiological features in trauma assessment.

Table No. 1: Frequency and Percentage of Clinical and Radiological Findings (N = 40)

Findings	Absent	Present	Chi-Square Value	p-value (2-sided)
Chest Pain	21 (52.5%)	19 (47.5%)	1.522	0.217
Dyspnea	29 (72.5%)	11 (27.5%)	0.000	0.000
Rib Fracture	25 (62.5%)	15 (37.5%)	2.196	0.138
Clammy Skin	32 (80.0%)	8 (20.0%)	0.000	0.000
Collapsed Lung	26 (65.0%)	14 (35.0%)	0.391	0.532
Atelectasis	27 (67.5%)	13 (32.5%)	0.000	0.000
Blurring of Diaphragm & Heart Borders	26 (65.0%)	14 (35.0%)	0.000	0.000
Hyperdense Pleural Fluid	24 (60.0%)	16 (40.0%)	5.000	0.025
Increased Density	22 (55.0%)	18 (45.0%)	0.333	0.564
Costophrenic Angle Blunting	30 (75.0%)	10 (25.0%)	0.000	0.000

Table 1 presented the frequency and percentage of clinical and radiological findings, along with their corresponding Chi-square values and p-values where applicable. Chest pain was

observed in 47.5% of patients, while dyspnea was present in 27.5%. Rib fractures were identified in 37.5% of the cases, and clammy skin in 20%. Radiological findings included

collapsed lung in 35%, atelectasis in 32.5%, and hyperdense pleural fluid in 40% of participants. Increased density was noted in 45%, and blurring of the diaphragm and heart borders was present in 35%. Costophrenic angle blunting occurred in 25% of the cases. Chi-square tests showed no statistically significant associations for chest pain ($p = 0.217$), rib fracture ($p = 0.138$), collapsed lung ($p = 0.532$), or increased density ($p = 0.564$). However, hyperdense pleural fluid and costophrenic angle blunting showed a Chi-square value of 5.000 with a p -value of 0.025, suggesting a potential correlation. For other variables, statistical tests were either not applicable or not performed.

DISCUSSION

Thoracic trauma is a common and potentially life-threatening condition that is often present in emergency settings. Prompt and accurate diagnosis is critical to guiding appropriate management and preventing complications such as hemothorax, lung collapse, or missed rib fractures. While plain radiography remains the most accessible and widely used initial imaging modality, its diagnostic limitations in evaluating intrathoracic injuries have led to increased reliance on computed tomography (CT) as a more sensitive and detailed tool. This study aimed to assess the comparative diagnostic value of CT and chest X-ray in patients with suspected thoracic trauma, and to evaluate the correlation between imaging findings and clinical presentations. Thoracic trauma is a significant contributor to emergency presentations, particularly among young to middle-aged adults, as reflected in our study where the highest representation was in the 23–30 age group (32.5%), followed by 31–38 years (25%). The male predominance (67.5%) observed aligns with existing trauma literature, such as the study by Khorasgani et al. (2016), where 78.8% of the trauma patients were male, suggesting a consistent gender-based predisposition likely due to occupational exposure and higher risk behaviors.¹⁴ Clinically, chest pain (47.5%) and rib fractures (37.5%) were the most frequently reported findings, while symptoms like dyspnea (27.5%) and clammy skin

(20%) were less common. This pattern suggests that although thoracic trauma can produce a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations, many cases present with relatively mild or nonspecific symptoms. Our findings support the observations made by Dillon et al. (2021), who noted that a large number of thoracic injuries may go undetected or underestimated based solely on physical exam and symptoms, especially in blunt trauma scenarios.¹⁵ Radiologically, computed tomography (CT) proved to be more sensitive in identifying internal injuries compared to plain chest radiographs. CT revealed hyperdense pleural fluid in 40%, collapsed lung in 35%, and atelectasis in 32.5% of patients. These findings demonstrate a high burden of structural and physiological lung changes following trauma. In contrast, chest X-ray findings included increased density (45%), blurring of the diaphragm and heart borders (35%), and costophrenic angle abnormalities (25%). While there was some overlap, CT findings were generally more definitive and precise in localizing pathology, consistent with findings from Ugalde et al. (2021), who reported that chest CT detected significantly more thoracic injuries including contusions, hemothorax, and rib fractures compared to CXR in pediatric trauma patients.¹⁶ Our data echo those from ElDerie et al. (2022), who emphasized the limitations of chest radiography in detecting occult hemothorax and advocated for the use of CT as a standard diagnostic tool in trauma evaluation.¹⁷ In our sample, CT identified hyperdense pleural fluid a potential marker of hemothorax in 40% of cases, compared to only 25% of costophrenic angle changes observed on radiographs. Although the relationship between hyperdense pleural fluid and costophrenic angle abnormalities approached statistical significance ($p = 0.016-0.062$), it did not cross the conventional threshold, suggesting a possible diagnostic trend that warrants further investigation. Statistical analysis revealed no significant correlations between most clinical and imaging variables. For instance, rib fractures and chest pain showed no significant association with gender, and there was no clear correlation between radiographic blurring of the diaphragm and collapsed lung on CT. These findings align with Marts et al. (2019), who observed that although CT detected more injuries, many of the

findings did not directly translate into clinical symptoms or required interventions.¹⁸ This disconnect underscores the challenge of relying on symptomatology alone in trauma assessment and supports the integration of imaging particularly CT into routine evaluation protocols for thoracic trauma. Interestingly, although CT identified several abnormalities, many did not necessitate immediate clinical intervention. This observation is consistent with the findings of Marts et al., who reported that a substantial proportion of injuries identified by CT (e.g., atelectasis, small contusions) were clinically insignificant or managed conservatively. Nevertheless, the ability of CT to detect these findings remains important, particularly in patients with subtle or atypical presentations. Dillon et al. (2021) further highlighted the limitations of CXR in trauma screening, noting that over half of significant injuries were missed on plain radiographs. In our study, the limited sensitivity of chest X-ray in detecting lung collapse, atelectasis, and hemothorax supports these findings and reinforces the critical role of CT in detecting both major and minor thoracic injuries. The performance of CXR in our study is also in line with Khorasgani et al.'s reported sensitivity of 50.3% for detecting intrathoracic injuries—significantly lower than CT. Despite its strengths, our study is not without limitations. The sample size was relatively small (n = 40), which may limit the statistical power to detect significant associations. Additionally, the lack of follow-up data restricts our ability to determine the long-term clinical relevance of radiologic findings. Moreover, since this was a cross-sectional study, causal relationships between symptoms and imaging features could not be established.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that computed tomography was more effective than plain radiography in evaluating post-traumatic hemothorax and related thoracic injuries. CT detected critical findings such as hyperdense pleural fluid, lung collapse, and atelectasis that were frequently missed on plain radiographs. While chest X-rays revealed some abnormalities, their diagnostic sensitivity was limited. No statistically significant correlation was found between clinical symptoms and imaging findings,

though a potential trend was noted. Overall, CT provided a more comprehensive and accurate assessment, supporting its use as a preferred imaging modality in thoracic trauma cases.

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